

Searching for Dark Matter with Leptonic Semi-Visible Jets

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August 2024

Abstract

This study investigates the detection of dark matter via leptonic semi-visible jets at the LHC within a Hidden Valley framework. Various trigger strategies are analyzed, including missing transverse energy (E_T^{miss}), the scalar sum of jet transverse momenta (H_T), and leading jet transverse momentum (p_T). The analysis demonstrates that the E_T^{miss} trigger significantly enhances the signal significance over the background, outperforming other triggers such as H_T and leading jet p_T . Specifically, the E_T^{miss} trigger generates a signal significance that is at least 0.59 higher than other triggers and achieves a 1% higher signal efficiency. However, the overall signal sensitivity remains at 10%, indicating the need for further research to identify more effective detection methods.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The Standard Model & its Limitations

The standard model (SM) describes the interactions of all fundamental particles in the Universe. Developed in the 20th Century [1–3], the SM has seen many successes [4]. The SM categorises all fundamental particles into fermions and bosons. Fermions include quarks and leptons that contribute to visible matter, while bosons are the carriers of the fundamental forces. These particles are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The SM particles [5].

The SM provides a strong understanding of nature, but some questions remain unanswered by the framework of the SM. For example, the SM describes neutrinos as massless particles. However, through the observation of neutrino oscillation [6], a process where neutrino changes flavour (an electron neutrino can become a tau neutrino), it arises that neutrinos are not massless. This behaviour is not explained in the SM.

Interactions in the SM produce matter and antimatter in the same quantity despite a clear dominance of matter over antimatter in the observed universe. This issue is known as the strong CP problem and comes down to the fact that no observations have shown the strong force violating CP, even though its formulation does not disallow it [7].

The focus of this study comes from the SM's inability to account for dark matter (DM). DM and dark energy comprise 95% of the mass-energy content of the universe [8]. DM is thought to interact very weakly with the SM, making it impossible to directly detect within particle physics experiments. However, many theories of DM allow for detectable signatures within particle physics experiments. These predict that DM could be produced in high-energy collisions, leaving unique signals to be analysed.

1.2 Dark Matter

The observational evidence for DM begins with galaxy rotation curves. From Kepler’s Third Law and modelling galaxies similarly to the solar system, one expects the rotation velocity curve for galaxies to decrease at larger radii. However, this is not observed. Instead, the velocity curve stays constant at a higher radius [9], a figure of the predicted model vs observation is seen in Figure 2. This discrepancy is corrected if non-luminous mass exists that cannot be measured in the outskirts of a galaxy.

Figure 2: Galaxy rotation curves, expected behaviour (A) against observed behaviour (B) [10].

Since the discovery of galaxy rotation curves, numerous other observations have provided strong support for the DM model of the universe. For example, the anisotropy of the Cosmic Microwave Background radiation [11]. Consequently, there is a pressing need to develop a more fundamental model of DM that can explain these phenomena and integrate well with the SM and its possible extensions.

Weakly Interacting Massive Particles (WIMPs) are a leading theoretical candidate for DM. WIMPs are massive particles that interact via weak nuclear force and gravity but not through electromagnetic interactions, making them invisible to conventional detection methods. They naturally arise in many beyond-Standard-Model theories, such as supersymmetry, and are favoured because their predicted abundance from the early universe matches current DM density observations. WIMPs are searched for through a variety of methods, including direct detection via nuclear recoils, where detectors aim to observe the tiny kicks imparted to atomic nuclei by passing WIMPs [12].

1.3 The Hidden Valley Scenarios

The Hidden Valley (HV) scenario is a theoretical framework that posits the existence of a “hidden” sector of particles, which interacts with the SM only through a “portal.” This dark sector, or “valley,” contains DM and is characterized by its inaccessibility under normal conditions. However, high-energy collisions at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) can provide the energy

necessary to probe this hidden sector. Access to the dark valley is mediated by communicator particles[13], often described by a gauge theory that couples weakly to the SM particles. These mediator particles, such as dark photons or massive Z' bosons, facilitate the interaction between the visible and hidden sectors, leading to unique experimental signatures.

Figure 3: A visual depiction of how the Hidden Valley is accessed through high energy collisions [13].

The search for mediators predicted by hidden valley scenarios, such as the Z' boson or dark photon, is motivated by their potential to integrate with existing theories without disrupting known particles and forces. This compatibility enables hidden valley models to explore the nature of dark matter while maintaining consistency with other theoretical frameworks [14].

1.4 QCD Jets

Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) governs the behaviour of quarks and gluons through the strong interaction. In colliders such as the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), high-energy quarks and gluons are made. Due to colour confinement, these quarks cannot exist in isolation and instead undergo a process called hadronization, resulting in a shower of particles collectively known as a jet.

Jets are a fundamental construct in particle physics experiments. Because a jet can be formed from any high-energy quark or gluon, it gives rise to unique signatures that are crucial for identifying and studying various processes. Dijet events occur when a collision fragments into two distinct jets. These events are common at the LHC and are essential for probing QCD. The invariant mass of the dijet system can reveal resonances which indicate the production of new particles. For instance, a narrow peak might suggest the existence of a new heavy particle decaying into two jets.

1.5 Semi-Visible Jets

Hidden Valley scenarios introduce a dark sector which interacts with the SM through various mediators. One such mediator is a Z' gauge boson, which weakly couples to SM particles. Other hidden valley scenarios may involve new scalar particles[15], exotic fermions, or additional gauge bosons that facilitate interactions between the DM sector and the SM. These mediators can lead to unique signatures in particle collisions, providing potential evidence for physics beyond the Standard Model. In this model, the dark sector is a mirror of the SM, giving rise to unique collider final state signatures, one of which is semi-visible jets (SVJs).

SVJs occur when dark sector quarks undergo hadronization, leading to a dark shower similar to QCD. This process results in a mixture of DM states, which partially decay back to the visible sector, and partially remain stable and invisible to the detector. These stable DM states are measured as missing transverse energy (E_T^{miss}), and semi-visible jets are characterised by the amount of E_T^{miss} in the jet's direction. The amount of E_T^{miss} for these signatures is quantified using an “invisible fraction.” This fraction indicates how many DM particles in the dark jet remain stable and manifest as E_T^{miss} .

Previous studies of resonant production of SVJs have focused on observables to enhance the detection of mediator particles, typically targeting the dark Z' resonance [16, 17]. One such observable is the system's transverse mass:

$$M_T^2 = M_{jj}^2 + 2 \left(\sqrt{M_{jj}^2 + p_{Tjj}^2} E_T^{\text{miss}} - \vec{p}_{Tjj} \cdot \vec{E}_T^{\text{miss}} \right). \quad (1)$$

The transverse mass should be approximately equal to the mediator mass, as it includes visible particles and invisible dark sector components. This observable can be valuable for identifying the origin of the E_T^{miss} , ideally indicating the presence of the dark matter particles in the final state. However, even if the transverse mass can reproduce the mediator mass, it might still not be discriminatory enough due to the presence of the QCD multijet background, which can have similar final-state kinematic behaviour. Typical analysis involves examining observables and fine-tuning them to enhance signal sensitivity and minimize background contributions. For the dijet SVJ signature, the final state is not significantly different from the QCD multijet, making it challenging to identify distinct observables.

Figure 4: Production of semi-visible jets with leptons produced from dark hadron decays [16].

More recent studies have incorporated more complex signals, introducing not just the $SU(2)_d$ Z' , but also a $U(1)_d$ dark photon. This allows leptons to appear in the final state by decaying from a DM hadron, as illustrated in Figure 4. Constraining the search to non-isolated leptons within the jet reduces QCD background, thereby increasing signal sensitivity. This presents a strong candidate for a signal that could contain the Z' resonance, offering a method for identifying the presence of dark mediators.

2 Analysis Strategy & Results

2.1 Overlap Removal

In ATLAS, the reconstruction of particles is done independently of each other. If the electron reconstruction is changed, the jet reconstruction is not affected. This can lead to problems, most notably that the energy deposits can be counted twice[18]. This method measures the geometric overlap of two objects at a certain time and removes them using a predefined priority.

Typically, this removes muons that are within the radius of the jet. However, since this analysis looks at muons in the jet, the overlap removal process removes muons that are interesting for study in the analysis. Therefore, further analysis continues without performing overlap removal.

2.2 Observables

ATLAS measures quantities necessary for the analysis of interactions. The first of these is the transverse momentum p_T . This is the momentum of an individual particle in a direction perpendicular to the beam axis. Such quantities are important because they are Lorentz invariant. Another such parameter is the rapidity η . This parameter is an angle that determines the particle's angle with respect to the beam axis. It is defined as $\eta = -\ln[\tan(\theta/2)]$, another Lorentz invariant measure used. Finally, the azimuthal angle ϕ of each particle. These three parameters provide a complete description of the reconstructed particle's information.

E_T^{miss} is a per-event derived quantity that indicates the transverse energy imbalance. It is found by taking the vector sum of all p_T , and taking the inverse of the sum to compensate for this difference. This quantity is of primary importance to us, as it indicates the presence of particles that do not interact with the detector and is an indicator of possible dark matter particle candidates.

Using the above observables, several additional observables are defined. For example, the transverse mass M_T is observed and discussed in equation 1. However, many other definitions are defined, one of which is the separation of two objects (jets or particles) R .

$$\Delta R = \sqrt{\Delta\eta^2 + \Delta\phi^2}. \quad (2)$$

Where $\Delta\eta$ and $\Delta\phi$ are the differences in rapidity and azimuthal angle between the two objects. This separation tells us how spread away these two objects being considered are. It is an important parameter in the discussion of isolation in section 2.3.

Another observable defined by the above parameters is the transverse ratio, $R_T = E_T^{\text{miss}}/M_T$. This ratio gives a clearer image of the amount of missing energy that contributes to the selected events.

2.3 Isolation

Isolation [19] is a parameter used in particle physics to distinguish between prompt particles and those arising from jets. It is particularly significant in identifying particles produced directly from hard interactions, as opposed to those generated from hadronization processes or secondary interactions.

Isolation is defined as the sum of the transverse momentum (p_T) of all particles within a specified cone surrounding the particle of interest. Mathematically, it is expressed as:

$$\mathcal{I} = \sum p_T(\in \text{cone}). \quad (3)$$

Figure 5: An example of isolated (a) and non-isolated (b) particles.

Isolation helps to find prompt particles, not created from other processes such as jets, as seen in figure 5. These prompt particles typically exhibit low isolation values, as they have minimal

surrounding transverse energy. Whereas particles associated with other processes tend to have substantial energy within this cone.

By taking the ratio of this value with the particle of interest' p_T , the relative isolation is found, which is:

$$\mathcal{R} = \frac{1}{p_T^\mu} \sum p_T(\in \text{ cone}). \quad (4)$$

Where p_T^μ is the muons' transverse momentum. Normalisation allows for comparison of isolation and is considered from here onwards. In this analysis, the focus is identifying non-prompt muons, which are muons originating from the decay of the dark sector particle ρ_d , found within the SVJl.

Another isolation parameter within this study is the inter-isolation. This parameter defines how much each lepton l is isolated with respect to all other leptons l_k within a radius R_{iso} :

$$\mathcal{I}_{\text{int}} = \sum_{j \in R_{\text{iso}}} \frac{p_{T,l_j}}{p_{T,l}}. \quad (5)$$

This parameter has been shown to be effective in distinguishing relevant backgrounds[16], and therefore this parameter will be explored within this context.

2.4 Samples & Search Strategy

For this study, signal events are modelled at leading order (LO) in QCD with a Z' mediator mass of 3 TeV and an r_{inv} fraction of 0.7, following the prescription in [20]. The Pythia8 [21] Hidden Valley module [22] generates the dark hadrons. Simulated event samples describe the main background processes, including Z + jets and $t\bar{t}$. The Monte Carlo (MC) generated samples undergo processing through a detailed ATLAS detector simulation [23] based on Geant4 [24].

The full selection process is detailed in table 1, outlining the criteria applied to events in order to identify those of interest.

The cuts on jet multiplicity and kinematics (steps 2 and 3) are necessary pre-selections before applying the trigger. A minimum of two jets is required because the SVJl signal typically involves a dijet system. The kinematic cuts ensure that selected events are energetic and central, thus focusing on the most promising candidates for analysis.

After these pre-selections, the trigger is applied (step 4). The triggers, detailed in Section 2.5, are chosen to enhance the likelihood of selecting signal events. By setting a minimum on the transverse ratio R_T , this implicitly set a threshold for the missing transverse energy, focusing on events where the missing energy is significant compared to the dijet system.

The SVJl signature is expected to produce pairs of muons. Therefore, requiring a minimum muon multiplicity of two (step 7) ensures the retention of events that could potentially reflect the signal. A relative isolation criterion (step 8) is applied to these muons, allowing us to focus on non-isolated muons, as it is expected to originate from jets.

Cut Criteria	Description
1. Initial Event Count	Determine the number of events before applying any cuts.
2. Jet Multiplicity	Select events with at least two jets (≥ 2 jets).
3. Jet Kinematics	Require the leading and subleading jets to have transverse momentum (p_T) greater than 200 GeV and pseudorapidity ($ \eta_j $) less than 2.4.
4. Trigger Application	Apply trigger criteria as discussed in Section 2.5.
5. Azimuthal Angle Cut	Ensure ϕ between any jet and E_T^{miss} is less than 2.0.
6. Dijet Transverse Ratio	Require the dijet transverse ratio (R_T) to be greater than 0.1.
7. Muon Multiplicity	Select events with at least two muons (≥ 2 muons).
8. Muon Isolation	Consider muons with a relative isolation less than or equal to 0.3.
9. Number of Non-Isolated Muons	Continue with events having at least two non-isolated muons.
10. Muon Charge	Ensure non-isolated muons have opposite charges.
11. Isolation and Separation	Require that non-isolated muons satisfy $\mathcal{R} \geq 0.1$, and separation $\Delta R_{\mu,j} \leq 1.0$.

Table 1: Cut criteria for event selection.

Finally, the remaining muons are constrained by ensuring they have opposite charges (step 10), their invariant mass falls within the range of the ρ_d meson, and they are contained within the jets' radius (step 11). These additional criteria enhance the selection of muons that are consistent with the characteristics of the SVJl signal.

2.5 Triggers

In particle physics experiments, triggers are essential criteria for determining which events are worth swiftly keeping for further analysis [25]. These experiments generate enormous volumes of data, often producing millions of events per second. However, only a small fraction of these events contain interesting or significant phenomena researchers are keen to study, such as rare particle interactions or decays.

Triggers function as a filtering mechanism, employing algorithms and conditions to evaluate events' characteristics in real-time. By applying these criteria, triggers help to reduce the data volume to a manageable level, ensuring that only the most relevant and potentially insightful events are stored for detailed examination. This process is crucial for optimizing data processing resources and focusing on the scientific goals of the experiment, such as discovering new particles or understanding fundamental forces.

The triggers employed in this study are based on straightforward conditions that events must satisfy to be considered for further selection. The criteria used are as follows:

Criterion	Description
Scalar Sum of Jet Transverse Momenta (H_T)	The scalar sum of the transverse momenta of all jets, known as H_T , must exceed 1000 GeV ($H_T > 1000$ GeV).
Leading Jet Transverse Momentum	The transverse momentum of the leading (highest energy) jet must be greater than 450 GeV ($p_{T,j_i} > 450$ GeV).
Missing Transverse Energy (E_T^{miss})	The missing transverse energy must be greater than 200 GeV ($E_T^{\text{miss}} > 200$ GeV).

Table 2: Trigger proposals.

By applying a trigger on the leading jet’s p_T , the analysis focuses on jets that not only contribute to a high total p_T but also possess individually high transverse momentum. This criterion ensures that the jets under consideration are energetic enough to originate from Z' particles.

Additionally, requiring a minimum level of E_T^{miss} in the event helps eliminate background processes that lack significant E_T^{miss} . This cut is essential for distinguishing events where genuine missing energy is present, often indicative of invisible particles, from those where it is not, thereby enhancing the sensitivity to the signal of interest.

2.5.1 Basic preselections

The basic preselection criteria, as outlined in Table 1, are applied prior to the third step in the cut criteria. The results of these preselections are detailed in this section, preceding any trigger considerations. Each observable is plotted in Figures 6a through 6i. The motivations for the selected triggers become evident due to the relatively uniform distribution of observables across the signal range. This uniformity supports the choice of triggers by indicating consistent signal characteristics across the observed parameter space. By focusing triggers on regions outside the background peaks, the signal can be effectively enhanced.

The preselection has a signal efficiency of 47.9%. This is largely due to the selection of prompt jets with a high transverse momentum. The selection of these jets is required to ensure fewer events that are unlikely to contribute to the SVJl signal are analysed. These jet selections correspond to a 48.61% decrease in signal sensitivity, meaning nearly 50% of signal events are removed from consideration from the jet selection.

Cut Step	Signal	Zmu μ	$t\bar{t}$	Significance	Efficiency
1	8230286.0	5.551800139854643e+17	96561979719680.0	0.01104486022109308	1.0
2	7949224.0	3.641152946775936e+17	89325890961408.0	0.013172010872476176	0.9658502733592899
3	3948202.0	3816484316905472.0	1842413174784.0	0.06389439949072265	0.479716256501673

Table 3: A table for the preselection trigger.

Figure 6: Preselection observables.

2.5.2 H_T Trigger

A minimum H_T threshold of 1000 GeV is imposed at cut step 4 to enrich the event sample with high-energy interactions. This selection is motivated by the expected kinematic properties of Z' decays into multiple jets. The H_T requirement suppresses backgrounds from low-mass processes while maintaining a signal efficiency of 32.2% before muon selection.

Figure 7 contains the plots for the cut criteria outlined in table 1, with the Trigger $H_T > 1000$ GeV. The reasoning behind such criteria is due to the preselection indicating the background decreases significantly beyond this region, whereas signal has more energetic events and remains uniform.

Figure 7: cut criteria step 7 for H_T Trigger.

Figure 7 presents the distribution of all observables prior to muon selection. At this stage, the statistical significance stands at 0.118, suggesting a significant background contribution. To mitigate this, additional selection criteria were applied.

Figure 8 illustrates the isolation parameters employed in this analysis. A prominent peak in the relative isolation distribution for background events at $\mathcal{R} < 0.1$ justified the implementation of a relative isolation cut.

Figure 8: The isolation observables before they are cut in the muon selection checks.

Figure 9: cut criteria step 11 for H_T Trigger.

Figure 9: (cont.) cut criteria step 11 for H_T Trigger.

Cut Step	Signal	Zmumu	$t\bar{t}$	Significance	Efficiency
4	2646440.0	498198388932608.0	305607671808.0	0.11852984865880992	0.3215489122272246
5	2436701.0	459027716767744.0	25849974784.0	0.11370000807155911	0.2960651547264065
6	1820528.0	29252380524544.0	166763479040.0	0.335646626954392	0.2211986145559592
7	1317953.0	16478841602048.0	43731128320.0	0.3242359216486533	0.16013455730059425
8	1191514.0	4672754548736.0	22204041216.0	0.5498994838996942	0.14477190675827709
9	817596.0	554339139584.0	4434445824.0	1.0937572807179765	0.09933996214347607
10	721594.0	376725929984.0	2712190720.0	1.1714457194924985	0.08767539868452923
11	650544.0	231907934208.0	1691105920.0	1.345986843804552	0.07904264074435814

Table 4: A table for the cutflow for the H_T trigger.

The final selection criteria, as depicted in Figure 9, demonstrate a notable suppression of background events while preserving the majority of the signal. This optimization is quantified by a significance of 1.3. Although this significance is relatively modest, it indicates that the applied criteria effectively distinguish signal from background, reducing noise without proportionally eliminating signal events.

Notably, there is a significant peak observed in the dilepton invariant mass distribution (Figure 9f). This peak suggests the presence of a resonance that aligns closely with the mass of the ρ_d particle, as discussed in [16]. Such a peak may indicate the existence of an intermediate state, potentially corresponding to a hypothetical dark sector particle.

It is also noteworthy that the signal region, contains more non-isolated muons 8c compared to the background region. In the signal region, up to 7 non-isolated muons are observed, whereas the background region sees no more than 5 muons per event.

2.5.3 E_T^{miss} Trigger

A trigger of $E_T^{\text{miss}} > 200$ GeV is selected in order to ensure that considered events have enough missing energies to have a Z' candidate. The motivation for this trigger is clear in the falling nature of the E_T^{miss} background distributions in figure 6b.

The signal efficiency for the E_T^{miss} trigger is 32.0%. This indicates a similar level of signal being removed compared to the H_T trigger, with a significance of 0.119. The significance indicates that the trigger again performs similarly after simple preselections to the H_T trigger, figure 10, shows the signal and background distributions before muon selection takes place.

Figure 10: cut criteria step 7 for E_T^{miss} Trigger.

Figure 11: The isolation observables before they are cut in the muon selection checks.

Figure 11 displays all isolation observables before their selection criteria are applied, noted is the presence again of a peak in $\mathcal{R} < 0.1$ in the background, therefore by applying this selection provides a good handle on the background whilst maintaining signal. Note also the number of non-isolated muons found is distributed over a larger range for non-isolated muons when compared to the background.

Figure 12: cut criteria step 11 for E_T^{miss} Trigger.

Figure 12: (cont.) cut criteria step 11 for E_T^{miss} Trigger.

The final selection criteria for the E_T^{miss} trigger are illustrated in Figure 12. This selection achieves a significance of 1.94 and a signal efficiency of 10.0%. These metrics indicate that the E_T^{miss} trigger effectively suppresses background noise while maintaining a moderate level of signal sensitivity, surpassing the H_T trigger in its ability to preserve the signal.

Similar to the findings in the previous section, a notable peak is observed in the signal's dilepton invariant mass distribution with the E_T^{miss} trigger. This peak suggests the presence of a resonance consistent with the mass of the ρ_d particle, as discussed in [16]. Additionally, the signal region continues to exhibit a larger number of non-isolated muons compared to the background, with up to 7 non-isolated muons observed in the signal region, whereas the background region shows no more than 5 muons per event.

Cut Step	Signal	$Z\mu\mu$	$t\bar{t}$	Significance	Efficiency
4	2636104.0	31042595454976.0	332880543744.0	0.4706166587298058	0.3202930806298725
5	2320460.0	23824101801984.0	247382310912.0	0.4729581347621358	0.28194164710325054
6	2267567.0	22559080841216.0	243627720704.0	0.47486139265891397	0.27551495631591394
7	1662085.0	8914625101824.0	58727424000.0	0.5548504763450474	0.2019474749691247
8	1498303.0	2574318043136.0	27943200768.0	0.9288040352061637	0.18204746664013052
9	1010557.0	348089286656.0	5287668224.0	1.6999711126950692	0.12278512391824074
10	902930.0	226070331392.0	3337963520.0	1.885166722034844	0.10970828411723992
11	827864.0	180107509760.0	2217847296.0	1.9388121089328065	0.10058757985977522

Table 5: A table for the cutflow for the E_T^{miss} trigger.

2.5.4 Leading jet p_T trigger

The leading jet in each event is required to have a minimum transverse momentum $p_T > 450$ GeV. This is again motivated by the falling nature of the background distributions (figure 6f), whereas the signal region remains constant. By removing the lower p_T contributions, a comparatively larger background is removed compared to the signal.

The signal efficiency for the Leading Jet p_T trigger has a significance of 37.8%, indicating fewer signal events are removed after jet selection. This is largely again due to the constant nature of the leading jet p_T distribution, removal of low p_T jets does not correspond to a large number of events being removed. The significance is 0.109 for the jet p_T trigger, taking place before muon selection. The plots corresponding to this step are found in figure 13.

The isolation variables are plotted in figure 11. The isolation variables follow the same trend as in the E_T^{miss} and H_T triggers. The peak in $\mathcal{R} < 0.1$, as well as the number of non-isolated muons being higher than background samples still holds with this trigger.

Cut Step	Signal	Zmumu	$t\bar{t}$	Significance	Efficiency
4	3109118.0	742238531354624.0	418200649728.0	0.11408881627689192	0.3777654493273654
5	2866215.0	688054163472384.0	369095016448.0	0.1092398348952965	0.34825222648716136
6	2175821.0	52274109874176.0	254622072832.0	0.30020972415287545	0.2643676516446483
7	1566680.0	28180568080384.0	67794108416.0	0.2947702588836122	0.19035548645305198
8	1392358.0	6952151678976.0	31533072384.0	0.5268760823291684	0.16917488767552474
9	921044.0	755919421440.0	5902890496.0	1.0552453458284519	0.11190909628833653
10	820756.0	500216528896.0	3695087616.0	1.1562099855910257	0.09972384159698956
11	749581.0	375006625792.0	2563684096.0	1.2198876444694866	0.0910759793812742

Table 6: A table for the cutflow for the leading jet p_T trigger.

Figure 13: cut criteria step 7 for leading jet p_T Trigger.

Figure 14: The isolation observables before they are cut in the muon selection checks.

Figure 15: cut criteria step 11 for the leading jet p_T Trigger.

The distributions following the application of the final selection criteria for the leading jet p_T trigger are displayed in Figure 15. This selection achieves a significance of 1.21 and a signal efficiency of 9.11%. These metrics indicate that the leading jet p_T trigger effectively retains signal contributions without excessive removal, unlike the H_T trigger. However, it is not as effective as the E_T^{miss} trigger in optimizing the analysis.

Note that the peak within the m_{ll} distribution is present within this trigger once again and, as seen in figure 14, the peak in relative isolation and the number of non-isolated muons provide a clear difference between the signal and backgrounds.

2.6 Conclusions & ways forward

Table 7 is a table of each trigger’s final significance and efficiencies. It is clear that E_T^{miss} is the best-performing trigger for both signal efficiency and significance. This is likely due to the fact that by requiring a certain amount of E_T^{miss} , many background events would be ruled out due to them containing comparatively low amounts of E_T^{miss} . For example, the $t\bar{t}$ background process generally leads to E_T^{miss} in the form of neutrinos, which contribute to small amounts of E_T^{miss} within the detector.

Trigger	Significance	Signal Efficiency (%)
H_T	1.35	7.90
E_T^{miss}	1.94	10.06
Leading Jet p_T	1.22	9.11

Table 7: A table of significance and signal efficiency for each of the triggers proposed in this study.

The leading jet p_T and H_T triggers perform similarly, with the H_T trigger achieving a greater final significance value while the leading jet p_T trigger exhibits higher signal efficiency. This trade-off is likely due to the leading jet p_T trigger being less stringent compared to the H_T trigger. A p_T threshold of less than 450 GeV is less restrictive than an H_T threshold of less than 1000 GeV. Consequently, the p_T trigger allows more signal data to pass through than the H_T trigger.

A similar rationale explains why the H_T trigger results in a higher significance than the leading jet p_T trigger. The H_T trigger removes a substantial number of events, leading to the elimination of many background processes associated with low-energy background jets. This reduction in background events increases the overall significance.

This analysis utilized FastJet’s [26] anti- k_t jet clustering algorithm with a jet radius of $R = 1$. These jets negatively impacted signal efficiency after selection, suggesting that a different jet object should be used to handle jet inputs. This implies that future studies of a similar nature should consider employing alternative reconstruction objects to improve performance.

This feasibility study proposed a basic search strategy using standard $R = 1.0$ jets to search for the SVJL signal [16]. Among the three proposed triggers, the E_T^{miss} trigger performed the best, achieving the highest significance and signal efficiency. However, the study encountered issues with signal efficiency when using standard ATLAS objects. Therefore, it is recommended that alternative objects be considered in future studies of similar signals to enhance signal efficiency.

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Appendix

Figure 16 presents cutflow histograms that illustrate the number of events passing each selection criterion for each trigger. These histograms provide a step-by-step breakdown of event retention throughout the selection process, as laid out in 1.

(a) H_T trigger cutflow.

(b) Leading jet p_T trigger cutflow.

(c) E_T^{miss} trigger cutflow.

Figure 16: Cutflow histograms for each trigger: H_T , leading jet p_T , and E_T^{miss} . Each selection criterion is numbered according to Table 1.